

ENVIRONMENTAL PSYCHOANALYSIS IN T.S. ELLIOT'S "THE WASTE LAND"

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ABSTRACT

Environment is a prominent discussion of the day. It has been adopted as a universal topic. This paper attempts to introduce alternate understanding of the problem faced by communities, societies, and institutions. The problematic phenomenon that can not be solved in a single perspective. The environment is an interdisciplinary point of view. It is a multifacet and broad condition. Rapid social change and industrialization have shaped new behavior relating to waste and its treatment. It is impossible to work alone in the complexities of environmental and psychoanalysis issues. A reflection of environmental problems conceptualized at a global level has been seen as a serious expression and concern across the periods and nations. It has been expressed also in a genre of literary work. Through poem written by T.S. Elliot - "*The Waste Land*", It can be learned that the poem has been inspired by the representation of behavior, psychic expressions, forms, problems, communities, and even formal institutions. The poem is constructed in five parts, they are The Burial of the Dead, A Game of Chess, The Fire Sermon, Death By Water, and What the Thunder Said. Every part of the poem has revealed human psyche and behavior toward the aspects of nature - earth, water, air, space, weed and the other, through the implementation of figurative language, allusion, and other poetry devices. As a result of this writing, the writer introduces corruptive behaviors leading to environmental psychosis that has been envisaged long before nowadays global society arguing and countering the environment as a discourse of bargaining their position in coping natural resources.

Keywords: Waste Land, Psychoanalysis, environment, psychosis

INTRODUCTION

Today almost all of the discussion is focused on garbage, pollution and climate change. How garbage has become a word that can be directed to the metaphorical equivalent and also to the lexical equivalent. Many meetings from the grassroots level to high state officials have been and will be carried out with a discussion agenda on waste. The average meeting of these meetings pursued the pollution conditions caused by the modernization process, both in developed and developing countries. The issues that arise are not only ecological problems but also extend to economic, social, cultural, ideological and political issues. All problems have been triggered by the phenomenon of damage experienced by various layers of the nation, which can be assumed to be part of the excessive use of natural resources and does not heed the side effects of natural exploitation activities (UNEP, 2009). Modernization itself

is a change from what was originally a traditional society to a modern society. One of them is seen from how to dress. The existence of globalization and modernization is so influential on people's lives. However, we must be able to filter out what is good and suitable to be applied in daily life and which is not suitable. Like the use of communication tools and the internet. Of course both are very useful for daily life, however, usage should not be excessive because of the negative effects that will be caused by it.

Environmental phenomena are a global problem. All disciplines have examined the procedures for handling the environment in the world. The first environmental problem is pollution or environmental pollution. Air, water and soil pollution takes millions of years to be normal again. Pollution was simply waste, regardless of its source, which diminished value and was symptomatic of problems in products and/or processes (Lal, 2016). That all things cannot be denied in the

attainment of modern humanity are part of the results of exploitation of nature. Humans meet their needs by logging forests, mining, hunting animals, to the use of machines that result in increased pollution and global warming, as well as various natural disasters arise. But the emergence of industrialization has also caused environmental pollution which is increasingly worrying.

It is undeniable that the emergence of the era of industrialization marked by the establishment of factories that produce various kinds of human needs, has been able to improve living standards. The development of the industrial sector is quite high. This development on the one hand has positive impacts such as increased employment for the people, but on the other hand it also spurs negative impacts such as pollution and environmental damage due to waste treatment in the industrial sector that is less concerned about the environment. The industrial sector and motor vehicle fumes are the main sources of pollution (Awange, 2012). Heavy metals, nitrates, and toxic plastics are responsible for a variety of existing pollution. While water pollution is caused by oil spills, acid rain, urban run off.

The goal of sustainable development is to create and maintain prosperous social, economic, and ecological systems. These systems are intimately linked: humanity depends on the services of ecosystems for its wealth and security. Moreover, humans can transform ecosystems into more or less desirable conditions. Humanity receives many ecosystem services, such as clean water and air, food production, fuel, and others. Yet human action can render ecosystems unable to provide these services, with consequences for human livelihoods, vulnerability, and security. Such negative shifts represent the loss of resilience. (Folke et al., 2004)

PSYCHOANALYSIS

The discussion about psychoanalysis cannot be separated from Sigmund Freud's views and interpretations of the human world and its environment. Freud is known as a pioneer as well as a philosopher who bases the mental paradigm of personality, sexuality, sublimation, hysteria dreams and many things related to the existence of

human psychology (Lynn, 2002). All Freud methods are based on the workings of psychiatrist in expressing the problems faced by patients (Riviere, 2018). This method became known as psychoanalysis.

In psychiatric disciplines there is no other way to find the cause of a patient's psychiatric disorders except to invite the patient to perform verbal interactions or the interview process. The interview process will produce a record of events that form the basis of the search for the main problems faced by the patient.

The important thing in psychoanalysis is to pay attention to the client's state of resilience, which is a condition where the client protects himself so that feelings of trauma, and failure are not known by the counselor.

Some techniques in the theory of psychoanalysis are to open the unconscious nature (Beutel, Stern, & Silbersweig, 2003), including:

- (1) Personality analysis technique (Case histories)

The dynamic approach to healing personality disorders is carried out by looking at the dynamics of the primitive impulse (libido) towards the ego and how the Superego restrains the urge.

- (2) Free Association

Is a technique that gives freedom to the client to say whatever feelings, thoughts and reflections that exist in the client's mind without looking at the good or bad or logical so that the client can be open in expressing what is in his mind

- (3) Dream analysis

That is a technique to open things - things that are not realized and

- give an opportunity to the client for problems that have not been solved
- (4) Analysis of resistance
Aimed to be aware of clients for reasons - the occurrence of resistance. The counselor asks the client's attention to interpret the resistance
 - (5) Transference analysis
This technique will encourage the client to revive his past so that members understand the client about the influence of his past on his life at this time.
 - (6) Interpretation
Interpretation is the development of the beba association technique. When interpreting, the counselor helps the counselee understand past and present events.

On the other hand Carl Jung determined that the five main archetypes of people's collective unconscious are: anima, animus, shadow, person and self .

1- Anima

Anima means in the Latin soul and according to Carl Jung's collective unconscious theory defines the archetypal image of the eternal feminine in the unconscious of a man. Anima is the basic pattern that makes the connection between self-awareness and collective awareness, thus opening the path to self. Thus, the anima is the basic pattern of the female figure, which is present in the male unconscious. This is an archetypal image related to the eros principle and reflects the nature of men's relationships, especially with women. Anima is associated with high emotions and the strength of one's life. According to Carl Jung, male relational problems are often the result of unconscious identification with anima or anima projections in a partner. It must be considered that the anima figure is not a representation of a particular woman, but consists of a fantasy that is filled with emotional needs and experiences (**Brewster & Brewster, 2018**). The most representative figures of this archetype are the goddesses, famous women, mother figures, girls, witches and female creatures.

2- Animus

Ánimus means in the Latin spirit and according to the theory of the collective unconscious makes reference to the archetypal image of the eternal masculine in the unconscious of a woman. In other words, it is an archetype relative to anima in women. As in her feminine parallelism, the animus forms the relationship between self-awareness and collective unconscious, thus opening the path to self. Animus is the basic pattern associated with the principle logo and reflects the nature of the connection with the world of ideas and passion. According to Carl Jung, animus is the basic pattern of meaning. Thus, the most typical animus figures are father figures, famous men, religious figures, ideal figures and young people. According to the theory of collective unconsciousness, unconscious identification with animus or projections in partners usually results in feelings of disappointment with real people and results in vital difficulties and / or marriage (**Brewster & Brewster, 2018**).

3- Shade

The shadow is one of the main archetypes of the collective unconscious which presents two different meanings. On the one hand, shadows are archetypes that represent the totality of the unconscious. Second, shadow refers to the unconscious aspect of a person's personality, which is characterized by features and attitudes that I do not recognize as their consciousness (**Brewster & Brewster, 2018**) . Shadow is a very relevant archetype for conceptualizing the theory of collective unconscious, because it shows that all personal and collective psychic dispositions are not assumed by conscience because of their incompatibility with personality. Thus, the conscious personality rejects a large number of psychic elements that are not lost, but develops self-antagonistic agents in the subconscious. The antagonistic agent of the conscious self is represented through an archetype of shadow and is expressed through all personality traits and behaviors that are not accepted as their own and definitions, and which hide others.

4. People

That person is the archetype that is antagonistic to shadows. That is, this refers to the subconscious aspect of yourself that you want to share with others. The

archetypal person includes all the unconscious elements that a person adopts as part of his public image (Brewster & Brewster, 2018). Aspects that refer to the archetypes of people according to the conscious part of the individual, so that the individual uses it as a decisive part of himself.

5- Enough
 Finally, Carl Jung's fifth primary archetype is self, which is defined as the primary archetype of collective unconsciousness. This basic pattern represents the final step in the individualization process of the person. In this sense, it is understood that the self is a basic pattern of totality, which is experienced as a transpersonal force that bestows life (Brewster & Brewster, 2018).

PSYCHOANALYSIS METHOD

Psychoanalysis is a methodology adopted from the steps used by psychiatrists in exploring problems faced by a patient. The stages of psychoanalyst and psychiatrist can be compared as follows:

ENVIRONMENT PHILOSOPHY

This philosophy was born in line with the struggle of thought in order to understand the phenomena of crisis and environmental disasters that occur today. This philosophy questions the fate of the universe, the fate of the earth and the fate of living things, including humans, who have begun to be threatened by natural disasters. On the other hand this long-thinking struggle was born out of concern for prophetic calls to participate in overcoming crises and disasters not only at the technical level of praxis but also at the level of scientific philosophical reflection (Mizzoni & Jardins, 2006). Environmental philosophy emphasizes our understanding of the nature of the universe and the nature of life in the universe which can further determine our behavior as humans towards the universe and life in it

Antropocentric Paradigm (Man as the Center)

The point of view of pure and expedient capitalists deals with neo-classical economics, which theorizes under the basis of a utilitarian framework in a narrow rational understanding based on the interests of certain individuals. Individuals are given more privileges than collective needs and society is understood as a product of competition awareness in marketing tools (Galbreth & Ghosh, 2013). Anthropocentrism paradigm which views humans as the center

of the universe, where humans are seen to have a temporary value of nature and all of its contents are merely tools for satisfying the interests and needs of human life (Sarkar, 2014). This perspective causes exploitative attitudes and behavior without regard to nature and all its contents that are considered to have no value. In this paradigm humans are positioned as superior subjects and nature as inferior objects. Humans are no longer as earth pilgrims but as creators of the earth that are outside the laws and natural frameworks. Thus humans are more considered to have power over the exploitation of nature.

There is a belief that "all good things can be promoted through legitimate operations by the economic market". The role of government in this perspective is to protect every life, freedom and property rights. Nature has benefits only because nature is very useful for humans (Elliot, 2012). Thus, Departing from this, it is believed that there are no real environmental problems in the future since humans and technology become infinite and always adjust themselves

Ecocentric Paradigm (Comprehensive)

Ecocentrism is the perspective that ethical use is broadened to encompass the ecosystem community as a whole (Cocks & Simpson, 2015). Meanwhile, biosentrism is a perspective that ethical concepts are limited to living communities such as animals and plants. Ecocentrism is a continuation of the environmental ethics theory of biosentrism (Cafaro & Primack, 2013). Therefore this theory is often simply equated because there are many similarities. Namely the emphasis on breaking the anthropocentric perspective which limits the application of ethics to the human community. Both extend ethics to the wider community. In biosentrism, ethical concepts are limited to living communities (biotic), such as plants and animals. While in ecocentrism, the use of ethics is extended to the whole ecosystem community (biotic and a-biotic). It is needed with an enthusiastic approach as a center, based on the angles of the eyes of the intellects who see the nature of being involved in taking place in making a decision or thinking in a natural way of thinking in a natural way.

DISCUSSION

The First part of "The Waste Land" - *The Burial of the Dead* begins with a paradoxical expression. If we may observe the mention of April in various classical poems, April has the meaning of growth, the emergence of new things, optimism and beauty because April is the beginning of spring, which is always associated with the melting of glaciers slowly along with warming temperatures, which results water clarity, buds begin to grow, flowers begin to bloom (Badeck et al., 2004). However, the early part of the poetry of "The Waste Land" begins with the same gloomy which is expressed in April as the cruelest month, while the lilac blooming is associated with the emergence of the dead land - a contrasting expression which is usually in early spring - April, blooming flowers are always blooming depicted with praise of beauty and happy panorama, not with the phrase dead land.

April is the cruelest month, breeding
Lilacs out of the dead land, mixing
Memory and desire, stirring
Dull roots with spring rain.
Winter kept us warm, covering
Earth in forgetful snow, feeding
A little life with dried tubers.

The situation can be interpreted that the feelings of the speaker in the poem are in problematic conditions. If you view from the year of making this poem around 1922. The events that set it up were the first world war that lasted from 1914 to 1918 (Lieber, 2007). This war has the root of the problem at the peak of the achievement of modernization of the socioeconomic order of the community which resulted in spiritual degradation. Spiritual degradation is often manifested in various despairs which are initially based on the progress made by humans with their technological civilization, but in reality the progress of that civilization cannot satisfy the expected needs (Heiderberg, 2000). The overall tone of despair in this poem, combined with the description of empty land as a barren and dirty place, will be recognized by readers as a battlefield for World War I, which completely destroyed

almost everything with certain parts of Europe, burning the fields large grass and forest leaving only endless landscapes of mud, soil and death bodies.

Here is the man with three staves, and
here the Wheel,
And here is the one-eyed merchant, and
this card,
Which is blank, is something he carries
on his back,
Which I am forbidden to see. I do not
find
The Hanged Man. Fear death by water.
I see crowds of people, walking round in
a ring.

In the beginning part of the poem, readers are able to hear from a woman speaker named Marie who looks back wistfully at the memories of her childhood. Later, readers are invited to listen to someone sitting on the banks of the River Thames and complained about all the garbage, and then there was a woman chatting at the bar. However, one speaker who seems to be able to occupy all these speakers is the blind prophet Tessias, whom Eliot called "the most important figure of the poem." Because he is a prophet or "fortune teller," Tiresias can guide us through each scene at every point in history, anywhere in the world.

Madame Sosostris, famous clair
voyante,
Had a bad cold, nevertheless
Is known to be the wisest woman in
Europe,
With a wicked pack of cards. Here, said
she,
Is your card, the drowned Phoenician
Sailor,
(Those are pearls that were his eyes.
Look!)
Here is Belladonna, the Lady of the
Rocks,
The lady of situations.

At the end of the first part of the poetry of the waste land, pessimistic thoughts expressed by the speaker in relation to doubts that arise after seeing the gloomy phenomenon which is manifested in the

under brown fog of a winter dawn, which reflects the paradox of the winter conditions that should all dictate to the expression pure white. In general reasoning winter is synonymous with the presence of snow and ice which is always white. The brown color in the fog indicates that there is something wrong in the environmental conditions that are very much possible by the pollution conditions due to the very massive industrialization. Likewise, the conditions under the London Bridge below flow "a crowd", of course, the crowd that flows under the bridge is not a crowd, because under the London bridge flows the River Thames which is always full of water. This also underlies that the expression "Unreal City", which should be demanded by the city as an embodiment of advanced human civilization, gives a picture of civilization about order, cleanliness, rationality and beauty. The magnificent increasingly open eyes that the threat to alarm increasingly evident with the expression "death had undone so many". Death should be a certainty, but the speaker negates the death and makes it a delay and uncertainty. The severity of irregularities in natural management is entrusted in this poem in the question "Has it begun to sprout? Will it bloom this year?" The skeptical question will not arise when natural conditions are in good condition, because only natural conditions determine the growth and development of seeds planted, although this poem uses the metaphor "corpse" as a manifestation of grains planted before winter in the previous year and is expected to grow in the spring of the following year. "That corpse you planted last year in your garden,"

In the second part of the poem *The Waste Land*, *The Games of Chess* depicts a woman sitting in a luxurious room with a bright atmosphere by candlelight and wearing diamond jewelry that indicates that the social status of the woman is not an ordinary woman. Certainly the woman is from the upper social groups. It seems that women are used as a picture of achieving success that is equivalent to the material attached to the depiction of women sitting in chairs and in nice rooms with the various jewels they wear.

‘The glitter of her jewels rose to
meet it,
From satin cases poured in rich
profusion;
In vials of ivory and coloured glass”

In imaging in the lines of the poem above, women are depicted as creatures that must be alluring. For that, he must highlight the material characteristics. In general, women are described as being confined in domestic space. The cultural notions they contain are male and female equal, but their nature is different. Some thoughts consider women to be the objects of men's satisfaction. From the point of view of life, women are depicted that no matter how high women's education is and no matter how much their income, obligations are objects that are equated with property. In "modern" relationships, women are portrayed as being filled with worries that are not attractive or attractive. To be accepted, women need to be physically presentable. Seeing this phenomenon, there arises wrong perceptions and assumptions that demean women in relation to the problem of women as objects.

The qualities and attitudes that characterize womanhood as the inherent potential of a woman are actually becoming assets in a series of cultural industry production and markets. Women have even reawakened a sense of extraordinary enthusiasm and happiness in society that entertained themselves with a series of commodities in the window of popular culture,

“My nerves are bad tonight. Yes,
bad. Stay with me.
“Speak to me. Why do you never
speak. Speak.
“What are you thinking of? What
thinking? What?
“I never know what you are thinking.
Think.”

The third part of “The Waste Land” poem is *The Fire Sermon*, in this third part the speaker expresses his complaints about the River Thames, which is the setting of this poem. Pessimism about the environment in the Thames watershed is described as very

alarming, with the expression that in watersheds there are already many branches sticking in the mud and the many floating bottles and cigarette cutters that spread throughout the watershed have formed a stifling view even disgusting for a great river which is the pride of the people of Great Britain. The river's tent is broken: the last fingers of leaf

Clutch and sink into the wet bank. The
wind
Crosses the brown land, unheard. The
nymphs are departed.
Sweet Thames, run softly, till I end my
song.
The river bears no empty bottles,
sandwich papers,
Silk handkerchiefs, cardboard boxes,
cigarette ends
Or other testimony of summer nights.
The nymphs are departed.
And their friends, the loitering heirs of
city directors;

The condition of the Thames river as described above is an accumulation of community activities that have made the river as a dumping ground and other uncivilized activities. There has been massive degradation due to industrialization and moderation which is practiced in a way that does not pay attention to environmental sustainability.

The fourth part of “The Waste Land” poem is “Death By Water”, this section gives a description of a Phoenician figure named Phlebas who has sunk to death on his voyage. The speaker pointed out that after the death of a merchant can no longer count for losses, there is only the process of decomposition of the body. This indicates that humans will no longer talk about their lives, humans will also not find and boast memories during their lifetime. The process of decay in the end only leaves bones,

Forgot the cry of gulls, and the deep
sea swell
And the profit and loss.
A current under sea
Picked his bones in whispers. As he
rose and fell

He passed the stages of his age and youth

Some expert interpret that the third part of "The Waste Land" is a discussion of ideas of renewal and regeneration, some support some reject. This situation reflects the condition of the personality of the individuals who negate egocentrism. The contradiction between the person of the old man and the new man came to the fore after the conflict of the ego. In Freud the id of the superego ego becomes a determinant of personality for both the younger generation and the older generation.

The last part of "The Waste Land" begins with the contemplative attitude of the speaker in poetry to reflect on the true meaning of life and death. An invitation to look at our psyche with caution and patience. The speaker wants to show the natural condition if it does not contain water and is only composed of boulders and dusty roads.

Here is no water but only rock
Rock and no water and the sandy road
The road winding above among the mountains
Which are mountains of rock without water
If there were water we should stop and drink
Amongst the rock one cannot stop or think

The above problems have become the speaker's concern when there is an indication of shrinking water quality and the emergence of rocks and sand so as to show aridity, an area without vegetation, and not productive. The poet seems to invite the reader to explore the root of the problems caused by modern activity, and the reality depicted in the appearance of the River Thames which is dirty, dirty, and not interesting to look at. An unhealthy psychic site will emerge if the reality of people ignoring the nature is increasingly left and the damage to damage and unhealthy actions continue to be carried out on the surrounding environment.

This poem ends with the statement that all creatures need water, earth, air and even fire, but what is needed is natural elements which are in good condition and not

polluted. The reader is expected to be able to observe all the natural resources that have been provided for human survival, and compare them, what if natural elements are absent in human life.

Gaily, to the hand expert with sail and oar
The sea was calm, your heart would have responded
Gaily, when invited, beating obedient
To controlling hands

Before human progress was made with manufacturing and economic and market-oriented activities, abundant resources were able to improve human welfare and balance was always thought of. The same thing is expected in this poem that all human activities must be returned again to the khaliq who has provided them free of charge for humans and it is natural for humans to use them according to their needs, and to restore their conditions properly. Datta. Dayadhvam. Damyata,- Giving, mutual cooperation, and watching each other.

CONCLUSION

Overall the poetry of "The Waste Land" raises the issue of cultural and environmental deterioration in Europe, which is marked by industrialization which is massively carried out by its people without regard to environmental governance and good effects. This is common in various parts of the world with an industrialization process that is only concerned with economic considerations, so that industry players often take pragmatic policies and are reluctant to spend some of the profits to build waste and waste treatment, so that the environment is related to the effects of industrialization such as water, air, land, and other resources can be well maintained. "The Waste Land" poem shows that the phenomenon of disposed land that has been ruled out has resulted in huge losses to the sustainability of natural and human resources. This poem also invites readers to contemplate, -doing a deep thought, so that they realize that the responsibility to care for the environment is a shared responsibility. Good or bad depends on the environment of humans, which

incidentally every individual is a producer of waste and garbage.

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